

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF PRODUCT STOCK IN PRODUCT ORDERING AND SUPPLY

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Abstract: *Product stock plays a key role in product ordering and supply. The magnitude of the costs confirms that improving the efficiency of inventory management is an important issue. Therefore, the basis of the policy of the stocks carried by enterprises is the purchase and ultimately the decision on the optimal amount of stocks.*

This article describes the role and importance of product stocks in the order formation and supply system, and the role of stocks in the economy.

Key words: *Reserve, steady (static) state of the flow, shortage, types of shortage, reserve policy, current reserve, reserve reserve, technological reserve, types of commodity reserve, types of production reserve, types of reserve according to the purpose of optimal management, reasons for creating a reserve.*

The main part

The concept of stock is one of the main concepts in logistics after the concept of flow. The reserve is considered a steady (static) state of the flow at a small moment of time and reflects the accumulation of a homogeneous flow in itself.

The reserve is created in order to eliminate the shortage. Scarcity can occur in the following forms: natural scarcity, technological scarcity, and artificial scarcity.

In the logistics chain, the relationship between the consumer and the supplier is established based on the mutual balance of supply and demand. The ratio of demand and supply between the elements of the logistics chain is not always proportional. It is necessary to create a reserve to ensure proportionality.

A firm's marketing deals with merchandise policy, while logistics deals with inventory policy.

Enterprise marketing performs the following functions within the framework of the product policy:

1. Forms and expands the product range.
2. Develops the nomenclature of goods.
3. Manages the quality of goods.
4. Engages in product modification.
5. Develops new product samples.
6. Develops a forecast of demand for goods.

The reserve policy of enterprise logistics consists of forming all types and types of reserves necessary for the company's activities, determining their optimal amounts and effective management of reserves. As part of the reserve policy, the company's logistics department performs the following functions:

1. Determining the range of raw materials, material resources, components, semi-finished products and finished products that must be stocked;
2. Determining the optimal amount of reserve volume;
3. Control of reserve level;
4. Order Management.

Today's firms and enterprises spend a large amount of capital on reserves. In practice, all working capital available in the enterprise is a reserve. Therefore, the reserve is one of the factors determining the efficiency of the enterprise.

Reserves are generally divided into groups based on the parameters of space (location) and time (time). The amount of the reserve cannot be imagined without its time indicator.

According to the location and function of all goods, material resources in the economy, raw materials are divided into basic and auxiliary materials, semi-finished products, details, goods or finished products, spare parts for repair.

According to the purpose of use, reserves are divided into the following categories:

- 1) Technological reserves, resources moving from one link to the next link of the logistics system;
- 2) Current reserves, statistical average formed for the production period or reserves needed for one batch of goods;
- 3) Reserve reserves, reserves used in critical, emergency situations, and sometimes in cases of excessive delays in the fulfillment of orders.

Reserves are also categorized based on space and time parameters. That is, goods are classified according to the place (enterprise, organization, geographical location) in which material resources are created or located and their quantity at a certain time:

According to the location.

The total stock in the micro or macro economic system consists of stocks of raw materials, basic and auxiliary materials, semi-finished products or components, finished products, spare parts for repair.

These system stocks, in turn, are divided into production and commodity stocks.

Stocks of goods, in turn, are divided into stocks of finished products in the warehouse of the production enterprise, stocks in the trading sector, stocks on the road and stocks in trading companies.

Each link or organizational structure in the chain of consumers and suppliers acts as both a supplier and a consumer of resources at the same time.

Production stocks are formed in consumer joints, that is, in shops, while commodity stocks are formed in the assembly shop of the production enterprise. Stocks will be available in the channels of production enterprises and distribution sector. Stocks in the field of trade are divided into stocks on the road and stocks in trade enterprises.

The enterprise always has production and stock of goods.

Production and commodity stocks are divided into several groups according to their function. For example, commodity stocks are divided into the following groups:

1. stocks in the warehouse of finished products;
2. goods on the road;
3. reserves in a wholesale trade enterprise;
4. stocks in a retail enterprise.

Each type of stock is accounted for in kind and monetary measurements, as well as an indicator of how many days the stock is available.

To determine how many days of reserves are provided, the amount of reserves in natural measure is divided by the average daily output.

Production stocks are used to ensure production consumption. They must ensure the continuity of the technological process of production.

Commodity stocks are used to continuously meet consumer demand for material resources.

Production and commodity stocks are divided into current, guaranteed and seasonal stocks.

Current reserves are the amount of reserves at any time of this period, which ensures the continuity of the production process between deliveries of material resources, current reserves constitute the main part of production and commodity reserves. The amount of current reserves is constantly changing.

Guaranteed reserves are formed in order to continuously provide the consumer with resources in case of interruptions in the supply process, in cases of delays in delivery. In contrast to current reserves, the amount of guaranteed reserves will not change. This reserve will not be used if the work is organized in a regular manner.

Seasonal reserves are created based on the fact that the preparation and transportation of resources and their consumption should take place at a certain time of the year or at a certain moment of the period.

According to the purpose of optimal management of reserves, they are divided into the following types: guaranteed, current, marginal reserves.

Limit stock is used to determine when to place the next order.

Every manufacturing enterprise is constantly dealing with production and inventory during its economic activity.

These reserves make up the main part of the working capital of the enterprise. In some production enterprises, the amount of capital spent on these reserves is 60-70% of the working capital.

Conclusion

Inventory management is a problem common to all businesses. Creation, storage, control and management of reserves are required in the activities of production, trade, and service enterprises.

There are several reasons why it is necessary to create and optimally manage reserves.

One of the main reasons is to ensure the continuity of the production process. The stoppage of the technological process due to the lack of sufficient reserves can cause significant losses to the enterprise.

The second reason is the seasonality of the preparation of raw materials, which mainly concerns the activities of firms and companies engaged in the processing of agricultural products.

The third reason is the seasonal nature of changes in the price of raw materials used by manufacturers. That is, creating a sufficient amount of reserves when prices are low and using them in production when prices are high.

The main problem with the creation and maintenance of reserves is the fact that a large amount of working capital is "frozen" in the form of raw materials and tangible resources. This process is called immobilization of funds in economic literature. The higher the turnover rate of working capital, the more profitable the economy is. An increase in the turnover rate of working capital means a low volume of stock of raw materials and material resources and not being kept in stock for a long time. To achieve this, it is necessary to determine the optimal level of reserves and their optimal management is required. The analysis of statistical data shows that during the next decades, especially in the macroeconomics, the size of stock of material resources and the amount of expenses for their maintenance have a tendency to increase.

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